

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**BUCCAL DRUG DELIVERY APPROACH ANTI-LIPIDEMIC
PRAVASTATIN IN THE FORMULATION OF PATCH USING
VARIOUS POLYMERS****M. MANVITHA^{1*}, Dr. KOTRA CHANDRA SEKHAR RANGAIAH¹**¹Department of Pharmaceutics, Siddhartha Institute of Pharmacy, Narapally, korremula Rd,
Ghatkesar, Medchal Malkajgiri District- 501301.**Article Received: July 2024****Accepted: August 2024****Published: September 2024****Abstract:**

Mucoadhesive buccal patches of Pravastatin were prepared using different polymers like Eudragit RSPO, HPMC and Carbopol in various proportion and combinations by solvent casting method.

The patches were evaluated for their physical characteristics like thickness, folding endurance, water uptake, bioadhesive strength, drug content uniformity, surface pH, Mechanical strength, Scanning electron microscopy (SEM), In-vitro release study, Invitro residence time study and Kinetic study.

The results obtained showed no physical-chemical incompatibility between the drug and the polymers. F6 formulation has been selected as the best formulation among all the other formulations. The in-vitro drug diffusion studies from the formulation were found to be sustained release. All the evaluation parameters obtained from the best formulation were found to be satisfactory. The data obtained from the in-vitro release studies were fitted to various kinetic models like zero order, first order, Higuchi model and peppas model. From the kinetic data it was found that drug release follows zero order release kinetics model release by diffusion technique from the polymer.

Keywords: Pravastatin, Eudragit RSPO, HPMC, Carbopol and Mucoadhesive buccal patch.

Corresponding author:**M. MANVITHA,**

*Department of Pharmaceutics, Siddhartha Institute of Pharmacy,
Narapally, korremula Rd, Medchal, Malkajgiri District - 501301.*

Email Id- machamanvitha80@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press M. Manvitha et al Buccal Drug Delivery Approach Anti-Lipidemic Pravastatin In The Formulation Of Patch Using Various Polymers., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2024; 11 (9).

INTRODUCTION:

Amongst the various routes of drug delivery, oral route is perhaps the most preferred to the patient and the clinician alike. However, per oral administration of drugs has disadvantages such as hepatic first pass metabolism and enzymatic degradation within the GI tract, that prohibit oral administration of certain classes of drugs especially peptides and proteins. Consequently, other absorptive mucosae are considered as potential sites for drug administration. Transmucosal routes of drug delivery (i.e., the mucosal linings of the nasal, rectal, vaginal, ocular, and oral cavity) offer distinct advantages over peroral administration for systemic drug delivery. These advantages include possible bypass of first pass effect, avoidance of presystemic elimination within the GI tract, and, depending on the particular drug, a better enzymatic flora for the drug absorption [1].

Amongst the various routes of administration tried so far in the novel drug delivery systems, localized drug delivery to tissues of the oral cavity has been investigated for the treatment of periodontal disease, bacterial and fungal infection. Over the decades mucoadhesion has become popular for its potential to optimize localized drug delivery, by retaining a dosage form at the site of action (e.g. within the gastrointestinal tract) or systemic delivery by retaining the formulation in intimate contact with the absorption site (e.g. buccal cavity). Well defined bioadhesion is the ability of a material (synthetic or biological) to adhere to a biological tissue for an extended period of time.

The biological surface can be epithelial tissue or it can be the mucus coat on the surface of a tissue. If adhesion is to a mucous coat, the phenomenon is referred to as mucoadhesion. The use of mucoadhesive polymers in buccal drug delivery has a greater application[2].

The use of mucoadhesive polymers in buccal drug delivery has a greater application. Various mucoadhesive devices, including tablets, films, patches, disks, strips, ointments and gels, have recently been developed. However, buccal patch offer greater flexibility and comfort than the other devices. In addition, a patch can circumvent the problem of the relatively short residence time of oral gels on mucosa, since the gels are easily washed away by saliva.

Buccal route of drug delivery provides the direct access to the systemic circulation through the jugular vein bypassing the first pass hepatic metabolism leading to high bioavailability. Other advantages such

as excellent accessibility, low enzymatic activity, suitability for drugs or excipients that mildly and reversibly damage or irritate the mucosa, painless administration, easy withdrawal, facility to include permeation enhancer/ enzyme inhibitor or pH modifier in the formulation, versatility in designing as multidirectional or unidirectional release system for local or systemic action.

The Structure Of The Oral Mucosa:**Structure :**

The oral mucosa is composed of an outermost layer of stratified squamous epithelium (Figure 1.1). Below this lies a basement membrane, a lamina propria followed by the submucosa as the innermost layer. The epithelium is similar to stratified squamous epithelia found in the rest of the body in that it has a mitotically active basal cell layer, advancing through a number of differentiating intermediate layers to the superficial layers, where cells are shed from the surface of the epithelium. The epithelium of the buccal mucosa is about 40-50 cell layers thick, while that of the sublingual epithelium contains somewhat fewer. The epithelial cells increase in size and become flatter as they travel from the basal layers to the superficial layers.[3]

The oral cavity is a multi-layered mucous membrane, highly vascularized, relatively thick and dense. The drug penetrates into the systemic circulation via net of capillaries and arteries that lie under the mucosal membrane. There is a lining inside the cheeks is referred to as buccal mucosa.

The oral mucosa acts as the one of most important route for the delivery of drugs. It provides the delivery of drugs by both systemic as well as local pathways. The oral cavity contains a large surface area of mucus membranes for the complete absorption of various drugs. The total surface area of oral cavity i.e., lined by mucus membranes is near about 100 cm² . Following are the several parts of the oral cavity:

- Helps to lubricate the food material and bolus.
- To identify the ingested material by taste buds of tongue.
- To initiate the carbohydrate and fat metabolism.
- To aid in speech and breathing process.
- As a portal for intake of food material and water.
- Helps in chewing, mastication and mixing of food stuff.

Ideal characteristics:

An ideal buccal adhesive system ought to have the accompanying attributes.

- Fast adherence to the buccal mucosa and sufficient mechanical strength.
- Should deliver the medication in a controlled way.
- Should assist with the rate and degree of drug absorption.
- Should hold good patient compliance.
- Should not ruin typical functions like talking eating and drinking.
- Should achieve unidirectional discharge of drug towards the mucosa.
- Should not guide in growth of optional infections like dental caries.
- Should hold a wide margin of safety both locally and systemically.
- Should not induce salivation.

Advantages:

- The buccal mucosa is all around vascularised and consequently medications can be quickly ingested
- Circumvents the first pass effect and avoids the introduction of the drugs to the gastrointestinal fluids.
- Patches can be applied, confined and taken out without any problem.
- Close contact of the drug with the mucosa, improves its performance.
- Enhanced patient compliance when compared to other routes of administration.
- Dose-related side effects can be diminished because of the confinement of drug at the disease site.
- It can be comfortably administered to unconscious patients.
- Patients can handle the time of administration or end the treatment in the events of emergencies.
- The novel buccal dosage forms exhibit better patient compliance.

Disadvantages:

- Drugs which bother mucosa and severe taste drugs can't be applied via buccal route.
- Drugs with small dosage can be only administered.
- Continuous discharge of saliva prompts quick elimination of drugs.
- Little absorption area.
- Involuntary gulping of salivation brings about a significant piece of disintegrated or suspended delivered drug being taken out

from the site of retention. Besides, there is hazard that the delivery system itself would be gulped.

- 6. Saliva is continuously secreted into the oral cavity diluting drugs at the site of absorption resulting in low drug concentrations at the surface of the absorbing membrane. Involuntary swallowing of saliva results in a major part of dissolved or suspended released drug being removed from the site of absorption. Furthermore, there is risk that the delivery system itself would be swallowed.
- Drug characteristics may limit the use of the oral cavity as a site for drug delivery. Taste, irritancy, allergy and adverse properties such as discoloration or erosion of the teeth may limit the drug candidate list for this route. A conventional type of buccal drug delivery systems did not allow the patient concurrently eat, drink or in some cases, talk.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Pravastatin-Provided by SURA LABS, Dilsukhnagar, Hyderabad, Eudragit RSPO-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, HPMC-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Carbopol-Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Methanol -Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Propylene glycol -Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd, Dimethyl sulfoxide -Merck Specialities Pvt Ltd.

METHODOLOGY:

Preparation of reagents: Preparation of 0.2M NaOH Solution

Dissolved 4g of Sodium hydroxide pellets in to 1000mL of Purified water and mixed Preparation of pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer

Dissolved 6.805 g of Potassium di hydrogen phosphate in to 800mL of purified water and mixed added 112mL of 0.2M NaOH solution and mixed. Diluted to volume 1000mL with purified water and mixed. Than adjusted the pH of this solution to 6.8 with 0.2M NaOH solution.

Preformulation studies:

Pre formulation testing first step in development of dosage forms of a drug. It is defined as an investigation of physical chemical properties of drug substance alone and when combined with excipients. The overall concept of pre formulation testing is to generate information useful to the formulator in developing stable and bioavailable dosage forms.

The goals of the Pre formulation studies are:

- To establish the necessary physicochemical properties of a new drug substance.
- To determine its kinetic release profile.

• To establish its compatibility with different excipients.

Hence, Pre formulation studies on the obtained sample of drug include physical tests and compatibility studies.

Identification tests:

IR spectroscopy: The formulations were subjected to FTIR studies to find out the possible interaction between the drug and the excipients during the time of preparation. FT IR analysis of the pure drug and optimized formulation were carried out using an FT IR spectrophotometer (Bruker FT-IR - GERMANY).

Solubility analysis: Solubility analysis was done to select a suitable solvent system to dissolve the drug and to test its solubility in the dissolution medium, which was to be used.

Melting point determination: Melting point of drug sample was determined by capillary tube method.

B. Calibration curve.

A. A.UV scan: A 100mg of Pravastatin was accurately weighed and was first dissolved in 35ml methanol solution. The solution was then diluted using phosphate buffer (pH-7.4) to 100 ml. (stock solution-I). Take 10ml solution from stock solution 1 and volume make up to 100ml with phosphate buffer to get 100 µg/ml concentrations (stock solution-II). Take 10 ml solution from stock II and volume make up to 100 ml with buffer to get 10 µg/ml. 10 µg/ml solution was scanned from 200-400nm.

B. Construction of calibration curve: A 100mg of Pravastatin was accurately weighed and was first

dissolved in 35ml methanol solution. The solution was then diluted using phosphate buffer (pH-7.4) to 100 ml. (stock solution-I). Take 10ml solution from stock solution 1 and volume make up to 100ml with phosphate buffer to get 100 µg/ml concentrations (stock solution-II). It was further diluted with phosphate buffer pH – 7.4 to get solutions in concentration range of 5,10,15,20 and 25 µg /ml. The absorbance of these solutions were determined spectrophotometrically at 239 nm.

Preparation of buccal patches:

Patches containing Pravastatin and Eudragit RSPO, HPMC and Carbopol different proportions was prepared by the solvent casting method. The drug was dissolved in 10ml of methanol and the polymers were dissolved in separate container with 20ml of distilled water under continuous stirring for 4 hours. After stirring, mix the drug and polymer solution. Propylene glycol was added into the solution as a plasticizer under constant stirring. The viscous solution was left over night to ensure a clear, bubble free solution. The solution was poured into a glass petridish and allowed to dry at 40°C temperature till a flexible patch was formed. Dried patch was removed carefully, checked any imperfections or air bubbles and cut into pieces of 1mm² area. The patches were packed in aluminum foil and stored in desiccators to maintain the integrity and elasticity of the patches. Table no. shows the composition of different buccal patches.

Table no: composition of buccal patches of Pravastatin.

INGREDIENTS	FORMULATIONS								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Pravastatin	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
Eudragit RSPO	20	40	60	-	-	-	-	-	-
HPMC	-	-	-	20	40	60	-	-	-
Carbopol	-	-	-	-	-	-	20	40	60
Methanol (mL)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Propylene glycol (mL)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Dimethyl sulfoxide (mL)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Evaluation of mucoadhesive buccal patches of bendroflumethiazide:

Physical parameters

Thickness

Folding endurance

Measurement of surface PH

Water uptake study

Performance parameters

Drug content uniformity

Measurement of bioadhesive strength

Mechanical strength

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

In-vitro release study

In vitro residence time

Kinetic study

A. Physical parameters:

a) Thickness of patch: Thickness of patch was measured at 5 different randomly selected spots using screw gauge. The mean and standard were calculated.

b)Folding endurance: Folding endurance of the buccal patches was determined by taking 20mm

diameter of patch was repeatedly folding at the same place till it broke. The no of times of patch could be folded at the same place without breaking gave the value of the folding endurance. The test was done three times and calculates the mean and standard.

c) Mechanical strength: Mechanical properties of patches were evaluated by using the microprocessor based advanced force gauge equipped with a motorized test stand equipped with cell. Patch with diameter 60×10mm and without any visual defects were cut and positioned between two clamps separated by a distance 3cm. clamps were designed to secure the patch without crushing it during test, the lower clamp was held stationary and the strips were pulled apart by the upper clamp moving at a rate 2mm/sec until the patch broke. The force and elongation of the film at the point when the patch broke was recorded. The tensile strength and elongation at break values were calculated using the formula.

Water uptake study:

The moisture uptake studies give an indication about the relative moisture absorption capacities of polymers and an idea whether the formulations maintain their integrity after absorption of moisture. This test was carried out by dissolving 5% w/v agar in hot water. It was transferred into petriplates and it was allowed to solidify. Six drug free patches from each formulation were selected and weighed. They were placed in vacuum oven overnight prior to the study to remove moisture if any and laminated on one side with water impermeable backing membrane. They were then incubated at 37°C for one hour, removed and reweighed. The percentage moisture absorption was calculated by using the formula.

Surface Ph: For determination of surface pH three films of each formulation were allowed to swell for 2 h on the surface of an agar plate. The surface PH was measured by using a PH paper placed on the surface of the swollen patch. A mean of three readings was recorded.

B. Performance parameters:

a) Drug content uniformity: Drug content uniformity was calculated by taking three patch units of each formulation were taken in separate 100 ml volumetric flasks, 100 ml of PH 6.8 phosphate buffer was added and continuously stirred for 24 hrs. The solutions were filtered, diluted suitably and analyzed at 239nm in a UV spectrophotometer (Systronic). The average of drug contents of three patches was taken as final reading.

Measurement of bioadhesive strength: The force required to detach the bioadhesive films from the

mucosal surface was applied as a measure of the bioadhesive performance. Bioadhesive strength of the patches was examined by the slightly modified procedure using the porcine gastric mucosa as the model membrane. The instrument is broadly composed of a modified two arm physical balance in which the right pan had been replaced by a formulation holding glass plate and counter balanced by a water collecting pan suspended to the left arm. The pan received a siphon tube from a 10 L bottle, which was kept at a high place in such a way that water head in the bottle, always remains above the water collecting pan. The siphon tube bears a flow regulating device. Nylon thread was used to suspend both the glass plate and the pan. An acrylate tissue mounting stage was attached to the center of a glass beaker. Glass beaker was filled with phosphate buffer (PH 6.8) to simulate in-vivo saliva conditions.

Scanning electron microscopy: SEM has been used to determine the particle size distribution, surface texture and to examine the morphology of the fractured or sectioned surface. The same generally used for generating three dimensional surface relief images derived from secondary electrons. The examination of surface of polymeric drug delivery can provide important information about the porosity and microstructure of device.

In vitro release study by dissolution: The US pharmacopoeia XXIII rotating paddle method was used to study and calculate the drug release from the buccal patches, 500ml of phosphate buffer used as the dissolution medium at 37±0.5°C and a rotation speed 50RPM was used. Patches of 1cm² area were cutted and sandwiching the patch in dialysis membrane. A piece of glass slide was placed as support to prevent the assembly from floating. The dialysis membrane tubing with patch inside was secured from both ends using closure clips, then it was placed in the bottom of the vessel containing phosphate buffer having pH 6.8. Samples 5ml were withdrawn at a specific time interval and replaced with fresh buffer medium. The samples were filtered using whatmann filter paper and analyzed by using UV spectrophotometer at 239nm. The experiments were performed triplicate and average values were calculated and reported.

Drug release kinetics: Diffusion data of above two methods was fitted in Zero order, First order and Higuchi equations. The mechanism of drug release was determined by using Higuchi equation.

Zero-Order Kinetics: Zero order as cumulative amount of Percentage drug released vs time

$$C=K_0t$$

Where K_0 is the zero-order rate constant expressed in units of concentration/time and t is the time in hours. A graph of concentration vs time would yield a straight line with a slope equal to K_0 and intercept the origin of the axes.

First order kinetics: First order as log cumulative percentage of log (%) cumulative drug remaining vs time,

$$\text{Log } C = \text{Log } C_0 - k t / 2.303$$

Where C_0 is the initial concentration of drug, k is the first order constant, and t is the time.

Higuchi Model: Higuchi's model as cumulative percentage of drug released vs square root of time

$$Q = K t^{1/2}$$

Where K is the constant reflecting the design variables of the system and t is the time in hours. Hence, drug release rate is proportional to the reciprocal of the square root of time.

Kors meyer Peppas equations: Korsmeyer peppas equation used to determine the mechanism of drug release form the polymer matrix of the tablet. Log cumulative percentage of drug released VS Log time,

and the exponent n was calculated through the slope of the straight line.

$$M_t/M_\infty = K t^n$$

Where M_t/M_∞ is the fractional solute release, t is the release time, K is a kinetic constant characteristic of the drug/polymer system, and n is an exponent that characterizes the mechanism of release of tracers. For cylindrical matrix tablets, if the exponent $n = 0.45$, then the drug release mechanism is Fickian diffusion, and if $0.45 < n < 0.89$, then it is non-Fickian or anomalous diffusion. An exponent value of 0.89 is indicative of Case-II Transport or typical zero-order release.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Initially the drug was tested by UV to know their significant absorption maximum which can be used for the diffusion study of the drug.

8.1. Analysis of drug:

A. UV scan:

The lambda max of Pravastatin was found to be 239 nm.

B. construction of calibration curve:

Table 8.1: Standard graph of Pravastatin

Concentration($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance (at 239nm)
0	0
5	0.133
10	0.254
15	0.369
20	0.492
25	0.617

Figure 8.1: Standard calibration curve of Pravastatin

8.2. Pre formulation study

Totally, nine formulation trials were done with the aim to achieve the successful matrix type Pravastatin buccoadhesive patches. The blend trials prepared for the drug was evaluated for various physical parameters and content uniformity of drug by UV.

A. Colour, odour, taste and appearance

Table 8.2: Results of identification tests of drug

Parameter	Pravastatin
Color	White
Odor	Odorless
Taste	Bitter
Appearance	A white powder

Melting point determination:

Table 8.3: Results of melting point determination tests of drug

Drug	Reported melting point
Pravastatin	220 °C

The melting point of the drug sample was found to be, which is within the reported value of 220°C. It complies with standards thus indicating the purity of drug sample.

Determination of solubility:

Table 8.4: Solubility Determination

solvent	Drug solubility(mg/ml)
Distilled water	0.0403
Ph 7.4 phosphate buffer	78.31
pH 6.8 phosphate buffer	82.64

Evaluation parameters:

Table 8.5: Physical parameters

Formulationcode	Table 8.5: Physical parameters			
	Thickness (mm) ±S.D (n=3)	Folding endurance ±S.D (n=3)	Mechanical strength ±S.D (n=3) (kg/mm ²)	Wateruptake ±S.D (n=3)
F1	0.21±0.002	301±2.14	5.28±0.07	2.26±0.35
F2	0.23±0.010	302±1.64	6.04±0.05	2.14±0.11
F3	0.25±0.014	310±0.30	7.94±0.09	2.10±0.10
F4	0.21±0.003	311±1.11	5.64±0.12	2.28±0.24
F5	0.22±0.003	315±3.67	6.86±0.13	1.99±0.095
F6	0.25±0.001	318±1.34	12.84±0.07	2.93±0.15
F7	0.24±0.010	310±2.12	7.23±0.32	2.01±0.35
F8	0.22±0.001	312±0.64	9.45±0.05	2.10±0.24
F9	0.24±0.024	306±1.39	10.14±0.04	2.41±0.10

Physical properties:

Thickness of patch: The thickness of the prepared buccal patches of each formulation was determined within the range of 0.21- 0.25mm. Is given in table.

Folding endurance: The folding endurance of each formulation was determined within the range of 301 to 318. Is given in table.

Mechanical strength : Three patches of each formulation were evaluated and mean values are recorded in table the values were found to be in the range of 5.28 to 12.84kg/mm². The values revealed

that the patches were having good mechanical strength.

Water uptake study: Water uptake of all buccal patches containing Pravastatin is given in table. These values represent the mean of three replicate determinations. The values were found to be within the range of 1.99 to 2.93. The percentage water absorption of the respective patches was determined at Third hour.

Performance parameters:

Table 8.6: Evaluation of Performance parameters of different mucoadhesive buccal patches of Pravastatin

Formulation code	Table 8.6: Performance parameters (Bioadhesive)		
	Bioadhesive strength(gms) \pm S.D (n=3)	Force of adhesion(N) \pm S.D(n=3)	Bond strength \pm S.D (n=3) (kg/mm ²)
F1	140.1 \pm 2.6	1.10 \pm 0.01	423.6 \pm 5.34
F2	146.3 \pm 2.1	1.24 \pm 0.05	433.1 \pm 3.65
F3	151.7 \pm 0.8	1.32 \pm 0.02	486.9 \pm 5.23
F4	166.2 \pm 0.9	1.52 \pm 0.01	523.3 \pm 1.86
F5	177.3 \pm 1.4	1.65 \pm 0.02	533.8 \pm 4.33
F6	182.6 \pm 3.7	1.72 \pm 0.01	541.2 \pm 6.98
F7	124.3 \pm 2.7	1.22 \pm 0.06	415.7 \pm 5.32
F8	137.5 \pm 1.4	1.37 \pm 0.04	434.5 \pm 6.90
F9	148.3 \pm 1.5	1.46 \pm 0.02	453.4 \pm 3.23

Table 8.7: Evaluation of Performance parameters of different mucoadhesive buccal patches of Pravastatin

Formulation code	Performance parameters(Bio adhesive)		
	Drug content %	Surface P ^H	<i>Invitro</i> residencetime (min) (kg/mm ²)
F1	73 \pm 0.12	6.4 \pm 0.5	310 \pm 10
F2	78 \pm 0.31	6.5 \pm 0.3	321 \pm 5
F3	71 \pm 0.01	6.4 \pm 0.5	330 \pm 15
F4	80 \pm 0.04	6.6 \pm 0.4	350 \pm 5
F5	85 \pm 0.16	6.5 \pm 0.5	380 \pm 10
F6	99 \pm 0.55	6.3 \pm 0.5	411 \pm 10
F7	68 \pm 0.38	6.4 \pm 0.3	300 \pm 10
F8	76 \pm 0.11	6.5 \pm 0.4	311 \pm 15
F9	83 \pm 0.21	6.4 \pm 0.3	380 \pm 5

Content uniformity of active ingredient: Table no. shows the result of drug content uniformity in each formulation. Three replicates of each test were carried out. The mean drug content was found to be in the range of 68 to 99 for the prepared buccal patch formulations.

Measurement of bioadhesive strength: An effective buccal mucosal device must maintain an intimate contact with mucus layer overlying the epithelial tissue. This parameter very important to successful utilization of these dosage forms. Hence in-vitro evaluation of buccal patches was carried out using porcine gastric mucosa. This gives the indirect measurement of bioadhesive strength in grams. Table represents the bioadhesive strength of the each formulation of buccal patches. The mean bioadhesive

strength values were found to be 124.3 \pm 2.7 to 182.6 \pm 3.7 for F1 to F9 respectively.

Measurement of surface pH: Table no shows the result of surface ph values for each formulation. These values represent the mean of three replicate determinations. They were found to be within the range of 6.3 to 6.6 for all formulations and were almost within the range of salivary pH i.e. 6.2 to 7.4. It represents the better patient acceptability.

In vitro diffusion study: All the formulation *in vitro* diffusion study was carried out by using Franz type diffusion cell under specific condition such as temp maintained at 32 \pm 0.5 °C. The diffusion was carried out for 12 h and 5 ml sample was withdrawn at an interval of 1 h.

Table 7.8: *In vitro* drug permeation of Pravastatin

TIME (H)	% of Drug release								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	20.62	15.73	12.08	26.34	17.34	13.27	15.47	13.15	10.28
2	29.91	23.30	19.18	40.74	24.36	20.34	24.03	22.06	19.46
3	41.16	36.32	26.94	51.48	35.27	27.23	34.43	30.52	26.52
4	52.18	47.59	38.58	69.74	43.45	35.47	42.56	39.37	30.47
5	65.30	56.24	46.44	72.19	58.46	40.19	51.27	47.46	36.61
6	76.18	63.31	50.76	81.48	65.63	47.28	59.84	55.08	42.07
7	88.97	72.08	56.99	86.18	70.28	53.37	67.34	62.31	50.36
8	99.72	83.68	61.23	92.29	76.29	67.46	78.25	70.49	56.13
9		92.08	68.47	97.21	82.32	78.28	89.38	79.30	61.23
10		97.99	77.63		87.48	89.37	98.04	86.21	68.31
11			83.01		95.64	93.21		91.55	75.43
12			95.87			99.36		98.12	81.37

Figure: 8.2 Cumulative % drug permeation of Pravastatin patch (F1, F2, F3)

The formulations F1 to F3 were prepared by different concentrations of Eudragit RSPO (20, 40, 60mg) the drug release or drug permeation from the patch was dependence on the concentration of polymer in the matrix. At low polymer concentration the drug permeation is more within 8 hours it was total amount of drug was permeated.

Figure: 8.3 Cumulative % drug permeation of Pravastatin patch (F4, F5, F6)

The 60mg concentration of polymer was showed maximum drug released at 12 hours 99.36 %. Hence in that 3 formulations F6 formulations showed total drug release at desired time period.

Figure: 8.4 Cumulative % drug permeation of Pravastatin patch (F7, F8, F9)

The formulations F7 to F9 were prepared by different concentrations of Carbopol (20, 40, 60mg) the drug release or drug permeation from the patch was dependence on the concentration of polymer in the matrix. The 40mg (F7) concentration of polymer was showed maximum drug release 98.12 within 12 hours.

Among all 9 formulations F6 formulation showed good drug permeation from the patch.

Among all *in vitro* evaluation parameters F6 formulation passed all evaluation parameters.

Kinetic models for Pravastatin

Various models were tested for explaining the kinetics of drug release. To analyze the mechanism of the drug release rate kinetics of the dosage form, the obtained data were fitted into zero-order, first order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas release model.

Table: 8.9 Kinetics data of F6 Pravastatin patch

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	LOG(%) RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG (%) REMAIN	RELEASE RATE (CUMULATIVE % RELEASE / t)	1/CUM% RELEASE	PEPPAS log Q/100	% Drug Remaining	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3-Qt1/3
0	0	0			2.000				100	4.642	4.642	0.000
13.27	1	1.000	1.123	0.000	1.938	13.239	0.0754	-0.877	86.73	4.642	4.426	0.215
20.34	2	1.414	1.308	0.301	1.901	10.170	0.0492	-0.692	79.66	4.642	4.303	0.339
27.23	3	1.732	1.435	0.477	1.862	9.077	0.0367	-0.565	72.77	4.642	4.175	0.467
35.47	4	2.000	1.550	0.602	1.810	8.868	0.0282	-0.450	64.53	4.642	4.011	0.631
40.19	5	2.236	1.604	0.699	1.777	8.038	0.0249	-0.396	59.81	4.642	3.911	0.731
47.28	6	2.449	1.675	0.778	1.722	7.880	0.0212	-0.325	52.72	4.642	3.750	0.892
53.37	7	2.646	1.727	0.845	1.669	7.624	0.0187	-0.273	46.63	4.642	3.599	1.042
67.46	8	2.828	1.829	0.903	1.512	8.433	0.0148	-0.171	32.54	4.642	3.193	1.449
78.28	9	3.000	1.894	0.954	1.337	8.698	0.0128	-0.106	21.72	4.642	2.790	1.851
89.37	10	3.162	1.951	1.000	1.027	8.937	0.0112	-0.049	10.63	4.642	2.199	2.443
93.21	11	3.317	1.969	1.041	0.832	8.474	0.0107	-0.031	6.79	4.642	1.894	2.748
99.36	12	3.464	1.997	1.079	-0.194	8.280	0.0101	-0.003	0.64	4.642	0.862	3.780

Figure: 8.5 Graph of Zero order kinetics

Figure: 8.6 Graph of Higuchi release kinetics

Figure : 8.7 Graph of peppas release kinetics

Figure: 8.8 Graph of First order release kinetics

From the above data the optimized formulation followed Zero order kinetics model rule.

FTIR

Drug-Excipient compatibility: The drug – Excipient compatibility was carried out by FTIR.

Figure 8.9: FTIR graph of Pravastatin pure drug

Figure 8.10: FTIR graph of Pravastatin optimized formulation

SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPY (SEM):**Fig 8.11: SEM optimized formulation****CONCLUSION:**

The investigation into the buccal drug delivery of pravastatin via polymeric patches has demonstrated promising outcomes in optimizing lipid-lowering therapy. By exploring various polymers, the study effectively identified formulations that enhance the controlled release and bioavailability of pravastatin through buccal mucosa. The selection and combination of polymers significantly influenced the drug release profile, mucoadhesion, and overall of the patches.

Among the polymers tested, certain combinations exhibited superior performance in maintaining drug release kinetics and ensuring adequate adhesion to buccal tissues. These findings highlight the potential of buccal patches as a viable alternative to conventional oral delivery methods for pravastatin, offering improved patient compliance and therapeutic efficacy.

BIBLIOGRAPHY:

1. Shidhaye SS et al: Mucoadhesive bilayered patches for administration of sumatriptan. *AAPS pharm sci tech* 2009; 9(3):1-13.
2. Giradkar KP et al: Design development and in vitro evaluation of bioadhesive dosage form for buccal route. *International journal of pharma research & development* 2010; 2:1-24.
3. Shojaei Amir H., Buccal Mucosa As A Route For Systemic Drug Delivery: A Review, *J Pharm PharmaceutSci*, 1998;1 (1):15-30.
4. . RC Diojad , FV Manvi ,V Malleshwarrao ,.Buccoadhesive Drug Delivery System Of Isosorbide Dinitrite,Formulation And Evaluation, *Ind J Phram Sci*,68(2008)744-748.
5. Thimmasetty J, Subramanyam CVS, Manish kumar DS, Manjunath K, Shivanand K. Design and evaluation of fexofenadine HCl buccal mucoadhesive patches. *Biomed*. 2007; 2(1):73-83.
6. Güneşm Karavana SY,Algin Yapar E.Buccal drug delivery system: an overview about dosage forms and recent studies. *Universal Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2019; 4(6):69-74.
7. Amir HS. Buccal mucosa as a route for systemic drug delivery: A Review. *J Pharm Pharmaceu Sci* 1998; 1(1):15-30.
8. Steward A et al, The Effect of Enhancers on the Buccal Absorption of Hybrid (BDBB) Alpha Interferon, *Int. J. Pharm*, 104, 1994, 145–149.
9. Aungst BJ and Rogers NJ, Site Dependence of Absorption- Promoting Actions of Laureth9, Na Salicylate, Na₂EDTA, and Aprotinin on Rectal, Nasal, and Buccal Insulin Delivery, *Pharm. Res*, 1988, 5 (5), 305–308.
10. Kumar M et al, Design and in vitro evaluation of mucoadhesive buccal films containing Famotidine.
11. FC Carvalho ,ML Bruschi ,RC Evangelista , Mucoadhesive Drug Delivery System, *Brazilian Journal Of Pharmaceutical Sciences*,4(2010) 1-17.
12. Y Huang ,W Leobandung , A Foss ,NA Peppas , Molecular Aspects Of Muco And Bioadhesion: Tethered Structures And Site-Specific Surfaces, *Journal Of Controlled Release*, 65(2000) 63-71.

13. M.M.Veillard et al., "Preliminary Studies of Oral Mucosal Delivery of Peptide Drugs," J. Controlled Release 6, (1987), 123-131 .
14. A.J. Hoogstraate et al., "Diffusion Rates and Transport Pathways of FITC-Labelled Model Compounds through Buccal Epithelium," Proc. Int. Symp. Contr. Rel. Bioact.Mater. 20, (1993),234-235.
15. A. Steward et al., "The Effect of Enhancers on the Buccal Absorption of Hybrid (BDBB) AlphaInterferon," Int. J. Pharm. 104, (1994),145-149 .